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Advanced Lithium-ion battery models for electric vehicles: Assessing the optimal order reduction technique[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Physics-based models could greatly improve lithium-ion battery management system's ability to estimate cell states. Integrating these models into battery embedded hardware can potentially extend the performance and lifespan of battery cells. Nevertheless, it is crucial to simplify this model to lessen the computational workload for a successful implementation in embedded microprocessors. This article uses the analytic hierarchy process to select the most suitable reduced-order technique for advanced models running in microcontrollers. The model's implementation feasibility is assessed based on weighted criteria significant for control-oriented applications, such as accuracy, execution time, required memory, observability, and controllability. The application of the process and the corresponding boundary criteria are exemplified in different evaluation scenarios, representative of the electrical vehicle market. The successful results of the proposed process validate its scalability and reproducibility in similar decision-making scenarios. This approach not only advances the integration of advanced physics-based models into lithium-ion battery management systems but also broadens the applicability of decision-making tools in control field.

1. Introduction

In the context of sustainability, developing more robust and reliable Lithium-Ion Battery (LIB) models is crucial, as accurate state estimation is the linchpin for making informed decisions throughout battery life and determining the optimal End-of-Life (EoL) threshold of Electric Vehicle (EV) [1]. Models must strike a balance between computational efficiency and representativeness of battery behavior to be suitable for real-time Battery Management System (BMS) applications [2]. Reduced Order Model (ROM) approaches play a central role in this process by simplifying complexity while retaining the essential dynamics required for accurate State-of-X (SoX) estimation across a wide range of operating conditions and degradation stages. Achieving this balance further depends on the constraints of different BMS architectures—centralized, decentralized, or modular [3]—which shape trade-offs between memory allocation, execution time, estimation accuracy, and control capability [2].

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List of Acronyms

AHP	Analytical Hierarchical Process
BCU	Battery Control Unit
BMS	Battery Management System
BMU	Battery Module Unit
CR	Consistency Ratio
DFN	Doyle-Fuller-Newman
DRA	Discrete Realization Algorithm
ECM	Equivalent Circuit Models
EoL	End-of-Life
EV	Electric Vehicle
FOM	Full Order Model
FVM	Finite Volume Method
IC	Integrated Circuit
KDE	Kernel Density Estimation
LIB	Lithium-Ion Battery
P2D	Pseudo-Two Dimensional
PDE	Partial Differential Equation
SPM	Single Particle Model
SPMe	Single Particle Model with electrolyte
SoC	State-of-Charge
SoP	State-of-Power
SoH	State-of-Health
SoX	State-of-X
SRAM	Static Random-Access-Memory
SS	State-Space
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
ROM	Reduced Order Model
TPA	Three Parameter Approximation

Currently, Equivalent Circuit Model (ECM)s are the prevailing approach for estimating State-of-Charge (SoC), State-of-Power (SoP), State-of-Health (SoH), and other SoX metrics in LIBs, owing to their simplicity and low computational burden [4]. They rely on equivalent electrical components and temperature- and C-rate-dependent lookup tables to capture battery behavior across different life stages [5]. Depending on configuration, ECMs can approximate impedance responses over the frequency spectrum by including non-ideal capacitors or Warburg elements to reproduce complex voltage dynamics at BMS sampling times [6]. Such extensions may raise the model order (up to the 8th) [5,7], while additional blocks for thermal dynamics can further increase it [8]. Although these refinements improve accuracy, they also add complexity and computational demand [7,8].

The variability of EV use cases further complicates modeling, requiring empirical models to capture multiple degradation modes and stages. This forces ECM lookup tables to cover a wide range of conditions and often adapt in real time [9]. To overcome these limits, ECMs are often coupled with adaptive filter-based or data-driven methods. However, these approaches raise computational cost, demand extensive characterization datasets [10,11], and remain constrained when interpolating outside or between lookup tables, leading to SoX prediction errors [12].

These drawbacks mainly stem from the limited physical insight of ECMs, which prevents them from capturing the transport dynamics governing lithium-ion behavior and long-term cell performance [13]. In contrast, physics-based models directly simulate lithium-ion transport within the cell's macroscopic structure using the governing electrochemical equations, eliminating the need for empirical characterization [13]. Among these, the Doyle-Fuller-Newman (DFN) model is the most widely used, offering valuable physical insights and more accurate SoX estimation [14,15]. However, similar to advanced ECMs, the Partial Differential Equation (PDE) expressions of Pseudo-Two Dimensional (P2D) models lead to very high computational demands, limiting control-oriented use [16]. This motivates the adoption of ROM approaches to leverage physics-based models in BMS.

Within P2D-ROM, two main strategies exist. The first simplifies macroscopic domains of the P2D Full Order Model (FOM), as in the Single Particle Model (SPM) or its asymptotic extension, the Single Particle Model with electrolyte (SPMe) [16]. The second focuses on further reducing the State-Space (SS) system using Discrete Realization Algorithm (DRA) [17]. Both offer multiple alternatives that trade accuracy for computational efficiency depending on reduction order and method characteristics [17].

Although science has advanced in the improvement of these strategies, none has identified the best one for on-board applications. Identifying the most suitable DRA within P2D-ROM for EV BMS requires multi-criteria decision-making tools.

Fig. 1. Methodology overview.

This work proposes a methodology for selecting the optimal ROM for diverse EV BMS hardware/software structures using the Analytical Hierarchical Process (AHP). Representative BMS configurations are evaluated, and the most appropriate DRA is selected based on architectural requirements. The results validate the method's reproducibility and provide insights to support broader adoption of representative P2D-ROM techniques in the automotive sector.

2. Methodology

This study presents a streamlined approach to support the complex decision-making process of selecting a DRA technique for implementing the ROM framework within an embedded BMS application scenario.

The decision-making process depicted in Fig. 1 is structured using the AHP, which decomposes the selection of the optimal P2D-based DRA-ROM into criteria, alternatives, and scenarios [18]. Each criterion—including accuracy, execution time, controllability, observability, and memory demand—is weighted according to its relevance in each BMS scenario, and normalized priority weights derived from the AHP pairwise comparisons quantify their impact. The assessed alternatives, such as TPA, Padé, and Ho–Kalman reductions, are scored against these weights to identify the best ROM configuration reliably and repeatably.

In parallel, as illustrated in Fig. 1, a two-branch equivalent circuit model (ECM-2RC) is evaluated independently as a practical benchmark of current modeling technology, enabling comparison of key criteria with the selected P2D-DRA approaches. This procedure allows identification of the optimal ROM for each BMS scenario and provides a reference for an established, representative LIB use case.

To define AHP inputs, first it is essential to define the boundaries and context of the representative use cases addressed in this work in order to define the appropriate criteria. The focus lies on the EV BMS market. This framework reflects the necessity of embedding P2D-ROM models to address various tasks commonly required in BMS development, influenced by the system architecture: centralized, decentralized, or modular [3].

The four representative scenarios considered in this study are:

1. **Compact BMS:** Focus on the optimal representation of SS-systems for implementation in centralized microcontroller architectures, addressing the trade-off between memory allocation and system manageability as key interests [3].
2. **Flexible & Efficient BMS:** Emphasize the reduction of BMS's microprocessor energy consumption to enhance performance in wireless and decentralized BMS architectures [3,19].
3. **Accurate State Estimation:** Use P2D-ROM models for implementing precise electrochemical SoX estimations in modular BMS architectures as observer blocks [20,21].
4. **Advanced Control Strategies:** Focus on the development of physics-based control algorithms to enable new control and optimization strategies in BMS, based on the modeled electrochemical insight of LIB-pack cells [22].

This study assumes the hypothetical requirement of building and integrating each scenario within a constrained framework defined by EV-specific microcontroller specifications. The chosen hardware/software setup serves as the reference for decision-making within the AHP. Specifically, the embedded hardware is represented by the Infineon® 32-bit AURIX™ TriCore™ TC39x

microcontroller family [23], while the LIB system is characterized by an average cell capacity representative of typical EV applications [24].

The definition of these scenarios within the target microprocessor influences the weighting of the criteria to generate AHP input. The assessment criteria weighted in each scenario are defined as follows:

- **Accuracy:** Assessed via the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between the simulated voltage outputs of the DRA methods and the reference voltage from the FOM-SPM simulation under the same driving cycle [16].
- **Execution time:** Measured as the mean runtime of the emulated core microprocessor during the execution of the DRA-SS systems over multiple driving cycles [25].
- **Memory usage:** Determined from the storage requirements of the SS system matrices (A , B , C , D) [2].
- **Controllability and observability:** Evaluated by comparing the corresponding gramian matrices of each SS system [26,27].

These criteria reflect the typical requirements faced by microcontroller software designers, providing a practical and robust framework for the AHP application methodology [2,11]. Details of each criterion and their respective weights in the decision-making process are described in Section 3.3.

In parallel, it is essential to define the applicable domain of the specific P2D-ROM model to identify the available DRA techniques and establish the AHP comparison framework.

Accurate electrochemical characterization of the P2D macroscale domain remains a challenging task [28]. In recent years, efforts have increasingly focused on developing comprehensive and reliable P2D parameter datasets to support physics-based modeling. A notable example is the dataset reported in [29], widely regarded as one of the most complete and trustworthy electrochemical DFN parameterizations, which was developed through a cell teardown process of an EV cell and is publicly available. In the present study, the dataset from [29], developed for the LGM50-T cell, was adopted to define the limits of the applicable P2D-FOM framework.

In this work, the P2D-ROM is simplified using the SPM approach. Within this framework, the particle subsystems exhibit output voltage dynamics that are highly sensitive to model order changes due to their multiple time-constant-dependent states, which strongly influence the dynamic response alongside overpotential effects. As a result, particle subsystems are prioritized in DRA simplifications and included as alternatives in the AHP evaluation [2]. In contrast, the electrolyte subsystem is less complex, can be accurately represented by first-order SS systems, and remains unchanged across P2D-ROM order variations. Therefore, SPM configuration in ROM does not need to be considered as an alternative in the AHP assessment, simplifying the decision-making process when using SPM [16,30].

Within the context of the SPM, potential DRA approaches are identified to enable the hypothetical implementation of P2D estimation functionalities on the selected hardware [17]. To ensure a robust evaluation, the comparison scope is defined to be broad and representative, encompassing a range of current approaches commonly employed in the P2D-ROM field [17]. The selected DRA techniques are:

- **Three Parameter Approximation (TPA):** Polynomial parameter approximation of PDE dynamics [31].
- **Padé Approximation:** Direct transfer function approximation, representing PDE dynamics with a rational function derived via low-pass filter techniques to fit frequency-domain characteristics [30].
- **Ho–Kalman Algorithm:** Indirect transfer function approximation; a data-driven realization algorithm using impulse response data to identify modal parameters [32,33].

These approaches provide a diverse set of options for evaluating DRA in the AHP assessment. Each is further detailed in Section 3.3.

Once the DRA alternatives are defined, the next step is to establish a framework and simulation testbed for their equivalent comparison within the AHP. Each DRA alternative is first converted into SS form, with multiple relevant model-order combinations for their respective solid particle concentration subsystems. This approach expands the range of alternatives while providing deeper insights for the AHP comparison. Then, each of these extended SPM-DRA alternatives are build and simulated using a representative BMS modeling software test procedures to evaluate their performance. To emulate the target microcontroller application, the simulation environment leverages MATLAB®'s parallel computing toolbox [34], executing each algorithm on a single computer core. The simulation environment generated establishes the foundation for a quantitative evaluation and comparison of the DRA algorithms performance results within the AHP weighted criteria from each scenario [18].

Establishing the optimal DRA technique for each assessed EV embedded BMS scenario allows determination of the maximum number of cells the selected software can handle within a typical LIB pack, clarifying overall BMS capabilities. This demonstrates how the AHP framework supports multi-criteria decision-making for P2D-ROM implementation and informs hardware/software architecture design. To provide a practical reference, the ECM-2RC, parameterized using the P2D-FOM pulse test data, is included as a benchmark. Although it cannot be directly compared to P2D-ROM models in the AHP due to structural SS-system differences in controllability and observability criteria [35], it enables evaluation in terms of memory usage, execution time, and accuracy, ensuring feasibility and practical applicability within constrained hardware/software environments.

3. Framework

Before determining the best ROM option for the BMS use case assessed, it is crucial to first outline the context for AHP application. Section 3.1 describes the specifications for the representative EV scenarios and the selected target microcontroller; Section 3.2 establishes the applicable electrochemical modeling context to delineate the boundaries of the applicable P2D-ROM domain; Section 3.3 reviews the DRA alternatives considered in the study, along with the criteria guiding the AHP; Section 3.4 presents the step-by-step procedure for incorporating the AHP concept to improve decision-making in P2D-BMS modeling framework; and finally, Section 3.5 outlines the development of the ECM-2RC environment, which serves as the basis for benchmarking the selected DRA alternatives.

3.1. BMS representative scenarios

To keep the use case broad and representative, the EV-LIB considered in this assessment reflects the average market segment, with a capacity not exceeding 71.7 kWh [24]. A 60 kWh, 400 V LIB configuration is chosen as the baseline [24]. For consistency with the electrochemical parametrization in [29], the LGM50-T cell is hypothetically adopted for pack composition, even though this cell type was primarily used in earlier EV LIBs, such as the first Tesla models [36]. The LGM50-T cell is selected due to the availability of a reliable electrochemical dataset for building the P2D modeling framework.

However, it should be noted that the LGM50-T, with a 5 Ah capacity, does not align with current market trends, which favor fewer parallel-connected cells with individual capacities ranging from 20 to 100 Ah [37]. Modern EV batteries increasingly employ higher-capacity cells to reduce parallel connections in LIB-pack branches [1]. To reflect these trends while retaining comparability in the final BMS dimensioning study – performed after applying the AHP and identifying the most suitable DRA for each scenario [38] – the LGM50-T cell is configured in a representative pack architecture of 110 cells in series and three branches in parallel (110S-3P) [37,39]. This adjustment modifies the original pack capacity but yields a practical and valid reference for assessing the requirements and integration potential of P2D-ROM models in current BMS technologies.

In terms of the BMS assumptions, the technical specifications of the microcontroller environment are shown in Table 1 [23].

Table 1
Infineon® 32-bit AURIX™ TriCore™ TC39x microcontroller family specifications [23].

Parameter	Value
Core number	6
Core running frequency	300 MHz
Flash memory	16 MB
Static Random-Access-Memory (SRAM)	6.9 MB

To further narrow the scope of this application, it is important to consider that, aside from models, embedded BMS must integrate other essential functionalities to ensure the safe operation of the LIB. These functionalities are represented by the BMS's software measurement data acquisition, protections, LIB Integrated Circuit (IC) communications... (Appendix A Fig. A.10 can be consulted for more detail) [10]. Therefore, it is defined in the assessed scenario that only a portion of the microcontroller's total flash memory is available for model-based cell state estimation and control-oriented purposes [11].

As not all features are as complex as the state estimators, only the calculation budget for the relevant features investigated and affected by this paper is listed in Table 2. The data presented in the following table represents the proposed battery pack structure of 110S3P cells based on a ECM 2-resistor-capacitor pairs.

SRAM column specifies the memory required to handle ECM's, required registers, in memory for all cells for all functionalities; the next column does the same for the non-volatile memory requirements; and the subsequent columns represent the execution time specified to run each functionality and the required accuracy associated to them.

Table 2
Memory and execution time requirements for different key BMS control-oriented features.

Feature	SRAM	Read-only memory	Exe. time	Req. accuracy
ECM-states	4.97 kB	5 kB	100 ms	1%–2%
SoC-estimation	4.72 kB	5 kB	100 ms	1%–2%
SoH-estimation	2.62 kB	2.2 kB	1 s	2%–5%
SoP-estimation	1.78 kB	2.8 kB	100 ms	–
Cell Balancing	1.03 kB	8.5 kB	100 ms	5%
LIB IC Comms	5.9 kB	15.65 kB	10 ms	–

A typical use case in the automotive industry is to define one or several software atomic units to contain the algorithms deployed for a single feature. Each software unit, when necessary, computes the results for all cells individually through a for-loop across the available number of cells.

Given the complexity of the new algorithms discussed in this paper, a novel paradigm of distributed computation across multiple microcontroller cores is a promising direction to maintain the real-time constraints of embedded BMS. However, such an approach introduces challenges related to synchronization of current–voltage measurements and the overhead of inter-core communication through shared memory. A detailed evaluation of this distributed paradigm will be addressed in future work.

For the present study, to ensure feasibility and provide a fair baseline for comparison, it is assumed that only a single core of the selected microcontroller is used for computation. In practice, each core could be assigned to a group of cells, but restricting the analysis to one core allows us to capture the most conservative and realistic case for current embedded BMS design. After accounting for other required variables and functionalities, it is estimated that only the 2% of the flash memory of the microcontroller – approximately 320 kB – remains available for implementing all DRA-SS systems selected by the AHP methodology, and allocating constants, variables and additional algorithms [40]. Additionally, it is assumed that SRAM data transfer is evenly distributed among cores, and only one of them is specifically dedicated to handling SS-system, states, and output registers in the microcontroller's volatile memory [23]. This context provides valuable information for determining weight priorities in each scenario of the AHP.

This framework is representatively emulated using MATLAB®'s Parallel Computing Toolbox, as the simulations can be configured to run on a single computer core. The results obtained can be scaled down to match the selected microcontroller environment characteristics.

Once the microprocessor model is defined, the specifications for the particularities of each assessed scenario are detailed in the following points.

- *Scenario 1: Compact BMS*

Centralized architectures are used in BMS design in small EVs due to the simplicity of this configuration [38]. However, this straightforward topology presents several limitations when complex models, such as those considered in this work, need to be integrated into BMS software. A key criterion for this scenario is the flash memory allocation required for P2D-ROM. Lower-order SS-systems allow that microcontroller dedicated flash memory – conceptualized in this case as a portion of the available memory within a single microprocessor – to compute the state of a greater number of cells through the central Battery Control Unit (BCU) block BMS structure.

Another critical aspect is execution time, as the BMS must compute the state of each cell within milliseconds and transmit it to the corresponding external control system to optimally distribute energy flows between cells while ensuring the safe operation of the LIB pack [21]. Consequently, system controllability, which enables rapid adjustments to cell states based on application needs, remains an essential but slightly less prioritized criterion in AHP decision-making [27].

Accuracy is important for optimizing BMS external control strategies, therefore, it closely follows the controllability criterion [32,33].

Additionally, accuracy ensures effective observability. However, observability holds a secondary priority in decision-making weights for this specific design case [35,38].

- *Scenario 2: Flexible & Efficient BMS*

Decentralized BMS is suitable for larger LIB sizes, as these designs distribute control across multiple Battery Module Unit (BMU) systems [39]. Each BMU has its own dedicated protection, state estimation, and control algorithms embedded in hardware [39], allowing the BMU systems to function independently. This conceptualization provides significant flexibility and scalability for BMU. Integration limits are directly dependent on the capabilities of the higher-order BCU that manages the BMU group [38]. Despite these advantages, this approach introduces complexities in communication, synchronization, and higher hardware costs [39].

Wireless decentralized BMS architectures eliminate wiring, reduce resources, decrease EV weight, and simplify installation [3]. However, wireless systems face challenges such as data transfer speeds, and signal interference, thereby increasing safety risks [39].

In this context, P2D-ROM execution time becomes a critical factor, as the sampling time influences the precision of model-based estimators and the effectiveness of control algorithms [19]. Lower execution times provide more frequent cell state estimation samples within specific time frames, thereby improving data availability. This additional information helps mitigate data transfer-related issues, such as data loss and corruption, typically associated with decentralized BMS architectures [39]. Furthermore, execution time is directly related to chip consumption, and its reduction can potentially enhance energy efficiency, particularly considering the large number of BMU that the decentralized BMS accommodates [19]. Lower-order SS-systems reduce execution time, making memory allocation a subsequent key priority [19]. Accuracy is important to provide the BCU with enough insight into each BMU state to ensure proper EV LIB operation.

The priority weights of observability and controllability are equally distributed since this scenario considers a general application of P2D-ROM in decentralized BMS [39].

Note that for this scenario the selected microcontroller framework is conceptualized to work as BMU within BMS structure.

- *Scenario 3: Accurate State Estimations*

Modular architectures are also used in EVs's BMS as these structures maintain flexibility, enabling them to interoperate with different BMU while being simpler than decentralized topologies [3]. In this case, the BMU only performs cell measurement data acquisition and low-level cell balancing and protection tasks [38]. SoC estimations and low-level LIB actions are

conducted by the BCU, which actuates the BMU systems [38]. In this scenario, the selected microcontroller represents the BCU.

This scenario focuses on a specific application within modular topology. It assesses the integration of P2D-ROM as an observer block to enable precise electrochemical SoX estimations, thus providing P2D domain insight in BMS [13].

Typically, the key priority for developing a model-based observer is accuracy, followed by the observability of SS-system states [20]. Memory allocation becomes the next priority, as it is essential to integrate observers into BMS software state machines while ensuring sufficient space for other functionalities and compacting the observer block in SS-systems [21]. Subsequently, execution time is key for defining the sampling rate of electrochemical state estimations [21]. The last priority for this scenario is controllability, as it does not significantly affect observer performance [35].

o *Scenario 4: Advanced Control Strategies*

Similarly to the previous scenario, this use case evaluates another specific software block for modular BMS topologies. It focuses on utilizing P2D-ROM to develop advanced control strategies that capitalize on the extended electrochemical insights provided by the P2D domain. This approach facilitates the implementation of additional operational boundaries, such as those extended by Li-ion concentrations in the solid phase along the electrodes, among other electrochemical variables represented in BMS. This broadened electrochemical insight potentially enhances the performance and safety of LIB systems [22,41].

Thus, the most critical aspect of this block is controllability [35], followed closely by execution time. Both criteria ensure efficient and rapid implementation of control strategies on each BMU [22]. Accuracy is also crucial, as precise state estimation of the SS-system enables the controller block to identify and apply optimal control strategies at cell level [32,33]. Then, memory allocation remains less relevant even though it is still essential to accommodate in the cell controller cell's SS-systems, since the allocation of these controller mechanisms can be included alongside state-machine functionalities within the available flash memory of the microprocessor [21]. While less critical, observability is still necessary, as it directly impacts the controller's performance based on control theory, by the definition of Popov–Belevitch–Hautus controllability test [35]. This scenario achieves the most balanced weighting within the assessed AHP criteria, a consideration that increases the depth and insight of the assessment.

Table 3 summarizes representative BMS scenarios, showing the processor role, its main tasks, and the priority order of the evaluation criteria (accuracy, execution time, memory, controllability, observability).

Table 3

Overview of representative BMS scenarios, processor roles, tasks carried out, and priority order of evaluation criteria (A: Accuracy, E: Execution time, M: Memory, C: Controllability, O: Observability).

Scenario	Processor role	Processor tasks	Criteria priority
1	BCU (Centralized)	- Compute cell states for all cells - Manage energy flow distribution - Basic monitoring	M → E → C → A → O
2	BMU (Decentralized)	- Protection - Low-level control - Communication with BCU	E → M → A → C = O
3	BCU (Modular observer block)	- Implement model-based observer - Estimate SoX - Integrate SoX into BMS state machine	A → O → M → E → C
4	BCU (Modular control block)	- Define and execute control strategies - Enforce operational boundaries - Optimize cell-level control	C → E → A → M → O

This framework guides the definition and weighting of criteria in the AHP implementation. All the qualitative assumptions made to characterize each scenario's criteria weights as AHP inputs are detailed later in Section 3.4.

3.2. P2D-ROM and DRA domain

The following mathematical development of the SPM provides a brief intuition into the context and expressions used in this work to define a ROM working environment. A detailed derivation of the SPM as a representative ROM is provided in [16], while the full P2D equations are presented in the Supplementary Material.

The SPM simplifies the DFN model by representing each electrode with a single spherical particle, approximating lithium-ion dynamics in the solid phase [16]. Volume averaging significantly reduces computational complexity while maintaining reasonable accuracy for terminal voltage prediction, though deviations occur at high C-rates or near operational limits [16,42].

To describe the lithium concentration in a spherical particle, Eq. (1) Fick's second law is employed:

$$\frac{\partial C_s^\pm(r, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{D_s^\pm}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial C_s^\pm(r, t)}{\partial r} \right), \quad (1)$$

where $C_s^\pm(r, t)$ is the lithium concentration in the solid particle of the positive (+) or negative (−) electrode [mol m^{-3}], D_s^\pm is the solid-phase diffusivity [$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$], and r is the radial coordinate [m] [16]. The boundary conditions are then expressed as in Eq. (2):

$$\left. \frac{\partial C_s^\pm}{\partial r} \right|_{r=R_s^\pm} = \frac{I(t)}{F a^\pm L^\pm A} = J^\pm(t), \quad \left. \frac{\partial C_s^\pm}{\partial r} \right|_{r=0} = 0, \quad (2)$$

where R_s^\pm is the particle radius [m], $J^\pm(t)$ is the lithium flux at the particle surface [$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$], $I(t)$ is the applied current [A], F is the Faraday constant [C mol^{-1}], $a^\pm = 3\epsilon_s^\pm/R_s^\pm$ is the specific interfacial area [m^{-1}] with ϵ_s^\pm the solid volume fraction, L^\pm is the electrode thickness [m], and A is the geometric electrode area [m^2] [32,33].

The surface concentration $C_{ss}^\pm = C_s^\pm(R_s^\pm, t)$ defines the stoichiometry in Eq. (3):

$$\theta^\pm = \frac{C_{ss}^\pm}{C_{\max}^\pm}, \quad (3)$$

where C_{\max}^\pm is the maximum lithium concentration [mol m^{-3}]. The corresponding open-circuit potential is then expressed as in Eq. (4):

$$OC P^\pm = f(\theta^\pm). \quad (4)$$

Surface concentrations also determine the ionic exchange current i_0^\pm and, consequently, the charge-transfer overpotential η_r^\pm [V], as shown in Eq. (5):

$$\eta_r^\pm = \frac{2\bar{R}T}{F} \sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{I(t)}{2a^\pm L^\pm i_0^\pm} \right), \quad i_0^\pm = k^\pm \sqrt{c_e^\pm (C_{\max}^\pm - C_s^\pm) C_s^\pm}, \quad (5)$$

where \bar{R} is the universal gas constant [$\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$], T the temperature [K], F the Faraday constant, a^\pm the specific interfacial area, L^\pm the electrode thickness, k^\pm the reaction rate constant, and c_e^\pm the electrolyte concentration [mol m^{-3}] [16].

The terminal voltage is obtained in Eq. (6):

$$V_t = OCP^+ - OCP^- + \eta^+ - \eta^-. \quad (6)$$

Therefore, the main challenge for solving the SPM is essentially reduced to obtain the surface concentration C_{ss}^\pm [16,42]. Among the various numerical methods, the Finite Volume Method (FVM) is the most commonly employed for solving the concentration equation (Eq. (1)) in spherical domains due to its suitability for such geometries [16]. However, this requires solving tens of state data points both in time and in the radial spatial domain, making it impractical for direct implementation of the SPM in FOM form in BMS embedded software [43].

To overcome this limitation, ROM-DRA techniques are employed.

3.3. ROM-DRA alternatives & decision-making criteria

The first step to simplify Eq. (1) is to reformulate solid particle models in a more manageable form, enabling subsequent dynamic analysis and replication of both SPM electrode particles using DRA algorithms. To this end, the concentration is expressed relative to an equilibrium state by introducing the incremental variable $\tilde{C}_s(r, t) = C_s(r, t) - C_{s,0}$ which represents the deviation of lithium concentration from its equilibrium value [32,33]. Being where $C_{s,0}$ the initial concentration value in the electrode.

Transforming into the frequency domain via the Laplace variable s , the concentration dynamics in each electrode are expressed using the Jacobsen–West transfer function framework [44]. Solving the resulting homogeneous differential equation by parameter substitution yields a general solution expressed as a combination of exponential functions [44]. The final transfer function at the particle surface boundary is then given by Eq. (7), where $\tilde{C}_{ss}(s)$ is the Laplace transform of the surface concentration deviation.

$$\frac{\tilde{C}_{ss}(s)}{J(s)} = \frac{R_s}{D_s} \frac{\tanh \beta}{\tanh \beta - \beta}, \quad \beta(s, r) = r \sqrt{\frac{s}{D_s}}, \quad (7)$$

Eq. (7) represents the target transfer function that the DRA techniques considered in this work aim to replicate, capturing the essential dynamic behavior of the solid-phase diffusion process [44]. Each SPM-DRA alternative evaluated here provides a different approach to deriving a discrete SS-system suitable for implementation in a BMS embedded framework. All detailed mathematical derivations, equations, and frequency-domain comparisons are presented in the Supplementary Material.

In the Padé and Ho–Kalman DRA alternatives, the positive electrode particle subsystem is chosen as the main focus for model order variation. This choice is motivated by its more complex diffusion dynamics, which require higher-order approximations for accurate representation, whereas the negative particle subsystem can be reliably captured using a low-order model without significant loss of fidelity. This behavior is evident when comparing the frequency-domain outputs of both DRA methods with Bode plots against the original target frequency response of Eq. (7), as detailed in the Supplementary Material. Consequently, the positive particle subsystem serves as the most representative benchmark for evaluating the trade-offs between accuracy and computational cost in the AHP assessment. The TPA alternative is not subjected to this consideration, as it inherently reduces Eq. (7) to a low-order system with two dynamic states per particle; thus, only this fixed set of states is considered in the present case.

To summarize the alternatives considered by the AHP, Table 4 groups each alternative, identifying the type of DRA technique used and the model order of both particle subsystems, as outlined in the previous points.

Table 4
AHP available alternatives: Summary.

Alternative	DRA technique	Particle SS-order ⁺	Particle SS-order ⁻
1	TPA	2	2
2	Padé	2	2
3	Padé	3	2
4	Padé	4	2
5	Ho–Kalman	2	2
6	Ho–Kalman	3	2
7	Ho–Kalman	4	2

The next step for defining AHP input process is to establish the criteria and weightings that guide the decision-making process. This conceptualization is crucial, as it determines which alternative is most suitable. The following points outline the key factors considered for the AHP:

o *RMSE*

Accuracy is assessed by comparing the voltage response of each ROM-DRA against a high-fidelity reference model (FOM). To ensure consistency across techniques, a common simulation testbed is defined. The FOM is built as an SPM discretized with the FVM, solving Eq. (1) over $R_s = 50$ nodes with a 1 ms time step. This resolution is necessary to solve particle concentration dynamics. The resulting terminal voltage from Eq. (6) FVM-based SPM configuration serves as the FOM reference for evaluating all DRA approximations under dynamic current excitation.

A representative 44-minute EV driving cycle is generated using the method in [45]. First, the cycle is simulated at pack level (60 kWh, Fig. 2a) and then scaled to the LGM50-T cell (Fig. 2(b)), preserving the same SoC variation and C-rate conditions. The adapted current profile is used both to generate the FOM reference and to excite the ROM models, providing a consistent basis for AHP analysis.

Fig. 2. Representative 60 kWh EV driving cycle (a) and adapted current profile for the LGM50-T cell (b).

The resulting stepped current profile has a 1 s resolution. For the FVM-based SPM, this signal is resampled to 1 ms and used to solve Eq. (1), generating the FOM terminal voltage through Eq. (6). For the SPM-DRA alternatives, the profile is instead resampled to 100 ms to match typical BMS sampling rates [38]. DRA SS outputs of Eq. (6) are then directly compared to the FOM reference at the same time steps. Finally, the RMSE is computed as the accuracy metric for each alternative.

o *Execution Time*

Subsequently, the simulation framework developed for assessing the accuracy criterion is also used to evaluate execution time. To represent a typical BMS iteration, a subset of the first 10 values – corresponding to 1 s – is extracted from the 100-millisecond rescaled current vector generated from the driving cycle. This shortened vector is then used to measure the total time required by each SPM-DRA alternative to simulate the terminal voltage output [25].

To obtain reliable insights, each alternative is simulated multiple times, as execution time may vary across iterations. The resulting execution times are recorded to generate a large sample for statistical analysis, allowing accurate evaluation of the computational performance of each alternative. Outliers and extreme values are excluded to avoid bias from sporadic system delays. Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) identification function, implemented in MATLAB®, is used to determine the most probable execution time and the 80% confidence interval [34]. The most probable execution time coincides with the mode, as execution time distributions are typically positively skewed. This measure provides a robust metric, directly extracted from the probability density function, to compare execution performance across DRA alternatives.

To further align the simulation conditions with a framework representative of the proposed microcontroller environment, MATLAB®'s *parfor* function from the Parallel Computing Toolbox is employed [34]. Each simulation iteration is distributed and executed independently on a single core, ensuring that only one core is involved per iteration and preventing interference with the measured execution time. The experiments are conducted on a Dell laptop with 16 GB of RAM and an 11th Gen Intel® Core™ i5-1135G7 CPU operating at 1.38 GHz, utilizing all four cores [46]. Considering 10,000 iterations per alternative, each iteration within the *parfor* loop evenly distributes four simulations across the four available cores [46].

o *Memory*

The memory criterion can be quantified by calculating the static memory size, in bytes, required to declare the variables and build the SPM-DRA equations and SS-system matrices.

For comparison within the AHP framework, variations in memory size are primarily influenced by the positive particle SS-subsystem model order.

Then, higher model orders for the LGM50-T positive particle SS-subsystem directly increase the memory required in SRAM and flash memory of the specified microcontroller.

Note that the order of the positive particle SS subsystem impacts the allocation of the model in flash memory. Additionally, for algorithm execution, the computational impact can increase exponentially with order extension [40]. Typically, in industry, memory profiling procedures are performed between volatile and non-volatile hardware components to gain insights into microcontroller memory consumption and management [40].

Since these types of assessments require specific implementations of the models in real microcontroller systems [40], and given that the present work aims to develop a methodology for generating a representative comparison framework for P2D DRA alternatives in general EV BMS scenarios, a detailed study of memory usage in a specific real microcontroller environment is considered beyond the scope of this work.

For the present case, a direct comparison of memory increments in bytes when increasing positive particle model order, is considered sufficient to validate the proposed methodology.

o *Observability & Controllability*

Controllability and observability are key properties of state-space (SS) systems that determine their suitability for control and estimation in BMS applications [35,43]. Controllability ensures that system states can be driven by inputs, while observability guarantees that states can be inferred from outputs. Full rank of the controllability matrix C and observability matrix \mathcal{O} (Eq. (8)) indicates that all states are fully controllable and observable [27].

$$C = [B \quad AB \quad \dots \quad A^{n-1}B], \quad \mathcal{O} = \begin{bmatrix} C \\ CA \\ \vdots \\ CA^{n-1} \end{bmatrix} \tag{8}$$

Beyond this binary assessment, gramians quantify the degree of controllability and observability. The controllability and observability gramians (W_c, W_o , Eq. (9)) for continuous- and discrete-time systems are computed via Lyapunov equations or matrix summation approximations [35]. Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of these gramians identifies the principal directions and magnitudes of control and observation, defining ellipsoids in the \mathbb{R}^n state space.

$$W_{o,c} \cdot \zeta = \lambda \cdot \zeta \tag{9}$$

To compare DRA alternatives of different model orders, the controllability and observability gramians are computed for each SS system using the methods described above. The principal eigenvalue (λ_1) obtained via SVD of each gramian quantifies the degree of controllability and observability of the most relevant state [43]. MATLAB®'s built-in functions are employed to directly extract the gramian matrices from the DRA SS-systems, and (λ_1) using SVD [34]. By consistently extracting λ_1 across all alternatives, including TPA, Padé, and Ho–Kalman DRA models of varying order, the approach allows fair comparison of systems with different dimensions. These values are then used in the AHP pairwise comparison to assess and rank the performance of each DRA alternative in terms of controllability and observability.

For more details on the theory behind these arguments and the calculation of controllability and observability inputs for AHP, consult the Supplementary Material, specifically the section dedicated to this topic.

3.4. AHP implementation

Fig. 3. Workflow of the AHP method applied to determine the optimal DRA alternative in the assessment.

Fig. 3 summarizes the AHP workflow applied in this study. Each block corresponds to a step in the decision-making process, from defining scenarios to selecting the best overall solution.

Step 1: Definition of scenarios and criteria. The process begins by defining representative BMS scenarios and selecting the evaluation criteria relevant for comparing alternatives. The scenarios frame the decision context, while the criteria establish the aspects under consideration.

Step 2: Weighting of criteria with Saaty’s scale. Criteria are compared pairwise using Saaty’s 1–9 preference scale [47], which translates qualitative judgments into numerical values. This results in the reciprocal comparison matrix S , where each entry s_{ij} expresses the importance of criterion i relative to j [18]. By construction, $s_{ji} = 1/s_{ij}$. The assigned values for each scenario are detailed in Appendix B.

Step 3: Consistency check (CR). The comparison matrix is normalized (Eq. (10)), and the weight vector for the criteria is obtained by averaging the row entries (Eq. (11)).

$$s'_{ij} = \frac{s_{ij}}{\sum_{k=1}^n s_{kj}}, \tag{10}$$

$$w_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n s'_{ij}}{n}. \tag{11}$$

The consistency of the judgments is verified using Saaty’s consistency ratio (Eq. (12)). If $CR \geq 0.1$, the pairwise comparisons must be revised; otherwise, the weights are accepted.

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RCI}, \quad CI = \frac{\lambda_{\max} - n}{n - 1}, \tag{12}$$

where λ_{\max} is the maximum eigenvalue of S , and RCI is the random consistency index.

Step 4: Evaluation of alternatives. For each criterion, the performance of the alternatives is compared. The quantitative results of the DRA alternatives are evaluated pairwise, as illustrated in Eq. (13). For example, if the accuracy obtained with the TPA method is $a = 0.01163$ and that of the 4th-order Ho–Kalman is $b = 0.00171$, the corresponding pairwise ratio is $\frac{a}{b} = 6.8027$. This ratio is then converted to Saaty’s scale using the transformation in Eq. (13), where r_{\max} denotes the maximum observed ratio to ensure full coverage of the 1–9 range. In this example, assuming $r_{\max} = 7.2582$, the resulting value on Saaty’s scale is 8.418. The normalized comparison matrix derived from these transformations allows the calculation of local priorities according to Eq. (14).

$$p = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \frac{a}{b} = 1, \\ \left(\frac{a}{b} - 1\right) \cdot \frac{8}{r_{\max} - 1} + 1, & \text{if } \frac{a}{b} > 1, \\ \frac{1}{\left(\frac{a}{b} - 1\right) \cdot \frac{8}{r_{\max} - 1} + 1}, & \text{if } \frac{a}{b} < 1. \end{cases} \tag{13}$$

$$w_a = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n s'_{ij}}{n}. \tag{14}$$

Step 5: Prioritization per scenario. Local priorities of the alternatives are aggregated with the criterion weights to obtain a global score per alternative in each scenario (Eq. (15)). The best-performing alternative is selected as the solution for that scenario.

$$W_{AHP} = w_a \cdot w_i. \tag{15}$$

Step 6: Global comparison across scenarios. Once all scenarios are assessed, the solutions are compared across contexts. This step identifies not only the optimal alternative for each specific scenario but also the most balanced solution overall, providing guidance for BMS design under varying requirements.

The numerical values used in each step are reported in Appendix B (see Tables B.11–B.14), and the full mathematical details are derived in the Supplementary Material.

3.5. Benchmark assessment

The ECM-2RC is parameterized using a pulse-test, typically at 1C, applied to the FVM-FOM reference model [29]. Specifically, the ohmic resistance, polarization resistances, and capacitances of the two-RC branches are extracted by fitting the transient voltage response of the FVM to a sequence of current pulses using MATLAB®’s ECM fitting block [34] (Fig. 4).

As shown in Fig. 4, this approach ensures that the ECM reproduces the dynamics captured by the reference FOM, while remaining a computationally lightweight. The ECM thus serves as a practical benchmark and is compared in each scenario only against the AHP-selected DRA alternatives in terms of accuracy, execution time, and memory allocation of the SS-system.

Fig. 4. FVM-FOM 1C pulse sequence fit with ECM-2RC.

4. Results & validation

Assumptions defined in Section 3.1 and detailed in the matrices of Appendix B (see Tables B.11–B.14). The Consistency Ratio (CR) was calculated for each case following the procedure in Section 3.4, and all values were below 0.1 (see Supplementary Material), confirming the consistency of the judgments expressed through Saaty’s scale. Fig. 5 shows the resulting criteria weights, which serve as inputs for decision-making in AHP. Appendix C Table C.15 shows Fig. 5 specific values. These weights reflect the qualitative assumptions made for each general scenario, but may vary depending on industry segment and specific application requirements [38].

Fig. 5. AHP proposed criteria weights.

Next, the results for the performance of the alternatives on each evaluated criterion is determined according to the definitions in Section 3.3. This phase establishes the main input for AHP. Table 5 summarizes the quantitative performance of all evaluated DRA methods, including the Padé and Ho–Kalman (HK) reduced-order models, alongside the reference benchmarks (FVM and ECM-2RC). The table reports accuracy (RMSE), memory usage, execution time, and system properties such as observability and controllability, which are key indicators of model fidelity and feasibility for embedded implementation.

Table 5

Quantitative results for DRA alternatives and reference options (FVM and ECM-2RC): RMSE for accuracy, memory usage, execution time, observability, and controllability.

Alternatives	RMSE	Memory (Bytes)	Execution time (μs)	Observability	Controllability
TPA	0.01163	72	55.12	3.991	23.660
Padé2	0.00595	72	55.69	3.999	0.895
Padé3	0.00284	100	57.26	8.984	5.874
Padé4	0.00160	136	59.14	15.882	22.418
HK2	0.00942	72	54.92	3.990	8.426
HK3	0.00362	100	56.36	8.393	65.738
HK4	0.00171	136	58.34	10.934	86.919
FVM	0	26 056	11,707.379	–	–
ECM-2RC	0.01352	36	34.55	–	–

For the accuracy criterion, Fig. 6 helps to interpret the results presented in Table 5, illustrating the terminal voltage output obtained when simulating P2D-ROM alternatives under the driving cycle current profile shown in Fig. 2(b). Fig. 6 highlights the

Fig. 6. Terminal voltage simulated output for FOM (black); TPA (red); 3rd order Padé (pink); and 4th order Ho–Kalman (blue). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

differences between the DRA positive particle SS-subsystem orders, r^+ , within a specific time frame. As expected, higher-order solid particle SS-subsystems yield greater accuracy, reflected in the lower RMSE values in Table 5. The reference FVM and ECM-2RC further emphasize the impact of the subsystem order on model fidelity.

Based on the numerical RMSE accuracy results from Table 5, a pairwise comparison can be established between the performance of the different DRA alternatives with respect to the accuracy criterion. The Table 6 presents the one-to-one ratios between the criteria extracted from RMSE results.

Table 6
Accuracy RMSE Ratios for AHP input.

B\A	TPA	Padé2	Padé3	Padé4	HK2	HK3	HK4
TPA	1	0.5119	0.2444	0.1378	0.8092	0.3111	0.1470
Padé2	1.9534	1	0.4775	0.2691	1.5806	0.6077	0.2871
Padé3	4.0912	2.0944	1	0.5637	3.3105	1.2729	0.6014
Padé4	7.2582	3.7157	1.7741	1	5.8732	2.2582	1.0670
HK2	1.2358	0.6327	0.3021	0.1703	1	0.3845	0.1817
HK3	3.2141	1.6454	0.7856	0.4428	2.6008	1	0.4725
HK4	6.8027	3.4825	1.6628	0.9372	5.5047	2.1165	1

Highlighted in blue is the maximum ratio in the RMSE ratio matrix from Table 6. This value corresponds to r_{max} defined in step 3 in the AHP process. Using the RMSE ratios from Table 6 the values can be mapped onto Saaty’s scale (see Eq. (13)), obtaining Table 7.

Following AHP guidelines, Table 7 is normalized so that the sum of each column equals one, providing the weighted inputs needed for the pairwise comparison analysis.

Table 7
Accuracy RMSE ratios in Saaty’s scale for AHP input.

A\B	TPA	Padé2	Padé3	Padé4	HK2	HK3	HK4
TPA	1	0.451	0.202	0.111	0.768	0.261	0.119
Padé2	2.219	1	0.417	0.224	1.742	0.548	0.24
Padé3	4.952	2.399	1	0.503	3.954	1.349	0.541
Padé4	9	4.472	1.99	1	7.23	2.608	1.086
HK2	1.301	0.574	0.253	0.138	1	0.328	0.148
HK3	3.83	1.825	0.741	0.383	3.046	1	0.412
HK4	8.418	4.173	1.847	0.921	6.758	2.427	1
SUM	30.72	14.894	6.45	3.28	24.498	8.521	3.546

Subsequently, the average of each row of the normalized matrix is obtained using Eq. (10), as shown in Table 8. Each value obtained constitutes the priority vector of importance ratios relative to the accuracy criterion.

Table 8
Accuracy RMSE Importance Ratios results from AHP implementation.

A\B	TPA	Padé2	Padé3	Padé4	HK2	HK3	HK4	Priority
TPA	0.033	0.030	0.031	0.034	0.031	0.031	0.034	0.032
Padé2	0.072	0.067	0.065	0.068	0.071	0.064	0.068	0.068
Padé3	0.161	0.161	0.155	0.153	0.161	0.158	0.153	0.158
Padé4	0.293	0.300	0.309	0.305	0.295	0.306	0.306	0.302
HK2	0.042	0.039	0.039	0.042	0.041	0.038	0.042	0.040
HK3	0.125	0.123	0.115	0.117	0.124	0.117	0.116	0.120
HK4	0.274	0.280	0.286	0.281	0.276	0.285	0.282	0.281
SUM	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

The resulting priority vector in Table 8 defines its importance on accuracy. Eq. (10) is then used to obtain the final priority vector, based on the specific weight assigned to accuracy, depending on the evaluated scenario. The final result guides the decision-making process in AHP for each of the DRA alternatives evaluated.

In the case of accuracy, the models with greater orders achieve better priorities due to the reduced RMSE values. In contrast, lower-order models have worse priorities. For models within the same order, the Padé approximation technique yields the higher priority values.

As stated in Section 3.4, the calculations for obtaining the remaining priority vectors for the other alternatives, derived from Table 5, can be found in the supplementary material. Additional details for the calculation of each alternative are provided in Section 3.3 and the supplementary material.

In particular, for the execution time criterion, it is useful to illustrate the procedure used to determine the most probable execution time of each alternative. Fig. 7 illustrates the results for each alternative: the shadowed areas represent the raw statistical datasets, the solid lines correspond to the fitted KDE, the dashed vertical lines indicate the mode (most probable value), and the green areas denote the 80% confidence intervals. For instance, Fig. 7(a) shows TPA (red), Fig. 7(b) Padé (magenta), and Fig. 7(c) Ho–Kalman (blue), with its model order referenced with r^+ . The mode values, corresponding to the most probable execution time, are used as trustworthy inputs for the AHP prioritization.

Fig. 7. Execution time KDE probabilities for (a) TPA, (b) Padé, (c) Ho–Kalman. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Following this procedure, the mode values for each alternative are obtained, defining the execution time criterion input for AHP as shown in Table 5 inputs. At first glance, it is evident that the model’s SS structure significantly influences execution time. Therefore, this criterion is particularly important, as it strongly depends on the selected DRA topology. For reference, the execution time of the FVM simulation using the same time step is also included.

Although computation times per cell iteration may appear similar among the DRA alternatives, small differences become significant when scaled across all cells in a battery pack. In such cases, AHP provides a robust framework by normalizing and weighting even closely spaced values, offering a clear comparison between alternatives and helping to identify the most suitable option in this complex, multi-criteria decision-making process.

Once all the AHP inputs are defined, the priority vectors for the criteria can be calculated following the same process presented for accuracy. The results are presented in Table C.16 in Appendix C, while detailed calculations are provided in the supplementary material.

At this stage, the priority vectors are adjusted based on the weights calculated for each criterion in the respective scenarios (see Table C.15 in Appendix C for detailed values). Using Eq. (15), the final priority vectors are obtained, guiding the decision-making process for the alternatives evaluated in each scenario. The final results of the AHP assessment are presented in Table 9, where the highest scores are highlighted in green, indicating the most suitable alternative for each scenario, while a visual interpretation is visible in Fig. 8.

Table 9
AHP final results for decision priorities across different scenarios. Winners for each scenario are highlighted in green.

Alternatives	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4
TPA	0.20164	0.21560	0.12798	0.16151
Pade2	0.16226	0.17452	0.12310	0.11299
Pade3	0.09383	0.08870	0.12116	0.10617
Pade4	0.10174	0.08921	0.20920	0.15522
HK2	0.20148	0.23706	0.13686	0.16399
HK3	0.12353	0.10800	0.11465	0.14006
HK4	0.11553	0.08691	0.16705	0.16006

Fig. 8. AHP results visualization.

In Scenario 1, where memory allocation and controllability are prioritized, TPA is the best option, only marginally ahead of HK2. For decentralized BMS structures (Scenario 2), 2nd order Ho–Kalman is the best option. In Scenario 3, where observer-related criteria dominate, 4th order Padé ranks highest. Finally, in Scenario 4, with stronger emphasis on controller performance, HK2 again leads. These results show that TPA and HK2 are most suitable under constrained conditions, while Pade4 is favored when accuracy and observability are key.

In any case, Table 9 and Fig. 8 highlight that, except for TPA, which presents worse results in the majority of the scenarios evaluated in the AHP assessment, the 2nd order Ho–Kalman and TPA alternatives are the most balanced on average, as shown (Table 10) by the total area covered by each alternative in Fig. 8.

Table 10
Balanced comparison among scenarios: Area, [μ^2], covered by each alternative in Fig. 8.

Alternatives	u^2
TPA	0.062
Pade2	0.041
Pade3	0.021
Pade4	0.038
HK2	0.068
HK3	0.030
HK4	0.035

Subsequently, to benchmark these optimal solutions, the ECM-2RC is evaluated under the same specifications as the DRA alternatives, considering accuracy, execution time, and memory requirements. Fig. 9a shows that its accuracy (RMSE = 0.01352) is higher than that of any SPM-DRA alternative. In terms of execution time (Fig. 9(b)), the ECM-2RC achieves 34.55 μs , significantly faster due to its direct implementation and simplified structure, with both the statistical dataset and the mode values confirming this result. The memory requirement is 36 bytes for allocating the 3rd order SS-system is nearly half that of the lightest DRA approaches.

Fig. 9. ECM-2RC performance.

Therefore, in Scenarios 1 and 2, where execution time and memory are the main constraints, the ECM provides a clear advantage. In less constrained cases – such as Scenario 3, where accuracy and state observability is critical – the Padé DRA offers clear benefits. In Scenario 4, where controllability is the focus, direct comparison between Ho–Kalman and ECM is not possible; however, the extended range of states that can be observed and controlled with an SPM-based model represents a significant advantage over ECM-type approaches [22]. This underscores the need for future work to bridge the efficiency of ECM with the advanced functionality of SPM-based models.

Finally, using the average LIB (110S-3P) selected in Section 3.1, a preliminary proposal for the BMS architecture can be defined for each scenario based on the optimal DRA obtained respectively.

Since the DRA optimum alternatives are already defined per scenario, the overall requirements needed to handle SS-systems, states, and voltage output variables in memory registers for each of the 330 managed cells can be determined based on model order.

Thus, assuming that all SS variables are handled in microcontroller memory as IEEE 754 single-precision variables (4 bytes) and that model iterations in real-time occur every 100 ms, the required data transfer for each SS-system can be determined by adding to the SS’s voltage output twice the length of the state vector (to account for all states at $k + 1$ and k instants). Besides, it should be taken into account that both solid particle SS-subsystems are included in this sum.

This calculation yields the memory requirements for a single SS-system. Considering all LIB-pack cells, it can be concluded that the second-order optimal DRA solution for the positive particle (from scenarios 1, 2, and 4) requires a data transfer rate of 118.80 kB/s, while the fourth-order optimal DRA demands 224.40 kB/s in scenario 3. In the case of the ECM-2RC the data transfer rate is 54.40 kB/s. The detailed methodology and assumptions behind these calculations are provided in the supplementary material associated with this work.

Based on the constraints of the selected microcontroller environment outlined in Section 3.1, it is evident that each optimal DRA structure can be accommodated within the available flash memory for all scenarios. However, higher data transfer rates in comparison to the ones proposed for the ECM case require deeper considerations in terms of defining the BMS architecture on each evaluated scenario. Specifically, distributed and modular BMS architectures must be designed to efficiently manage the memory workload. A centralized architecture in this case will not be an option, as it cannot handle the resulting data bus traffic with a single microcontroller.

However, since this work focuses mainly on presenting the methodology for integrating AHP in the context of EV-representative BMS, the secondary validation process in real embedded LIB hardware remains a consideration for future work.

Future efforts will focus on implementing optimal P2D-ROM within the high-level programming environment, enabling automatic code generation for AUTOSAR-compliant C code. This implementation will facilitate seamless integration into real automotive BMS hardware while ensuring standardization and interoperability with existing electronic control units. This is particularly relevant for investigating distributed BMS architectures with wireless communication systems. The use of an automotive-qualified microcontroller presents an opportunity to validate real-time performance under constrained computational resources, providing insights into the trade-offs between model fidelity and execution efficiency. Moreover, direct validation with real cell measurements will enable a comprehensive assessment of accuracy in comparison to state-of-the-art techniques.

The transition from a high-level coding environment model to embedded C code may introduce numerical precision issues, requiring rigorous verification and validation against the original physics-based models. Addressing these challenges will be crucial for ensuring model reliability, real-time feasibility, and practical industrialization-level applicability in next-generation battery management systems.

Furthermore, future research could extend the applicability of AHP to similar assessments in other ROM components, such as evaluating additional aspects of the P2D domain—including electrolyte dynamics or degradation effects—and comparing them with current ECM-based approximations. This extension would broaden the scope of the methodology and enable the representation of more complex P2D-based models.

5. Conclusions

This work demonstrates a step-by-step implementation of AHP to identify optimal DRA techniques for building SPM-based models in typical EV BMS architectures. The analysis shows that no single approach dominates across all criteria; rather, the optimal choice depends on the specific design focus.

Overall, the 2nd-order Ho–Kalman method provides the most balanced trade-off between memory efficiency, execution time, and controllability, while the 4th-order Padé method excels when accuracy is critical, achieving the lowest RMSE and closely matching terminal voltage outputs. Benchmarking with the ECM-2RC highlights that, although ECMs are highly efficient in memory and execution time, SPM-based models deliver superior state estimation and enhanced qualitative control—benefits that ECMs cannot achieve in embedded BMS environments. Nevertheless, BMS structures must be appropriately designed to accommodate these advanced features.

This study confirms the value of AHP as a structured decision-making tool for battery model reduction. By quantifying trade-offs between key criteria, the methodology guides the selection of the most suitable ROM for specific BMS architectures. Future work will focus on embedded validation on automotive microcontrollers, exploring wireless and modular BMS architectures, and extending the approach to other ROM domains, such as electrolyte dynamics and degradation modeling, thereby bridging the gap between high-fidelity electrochemical models and real-time BMS implementation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sergi Obrador Rey: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Lluc Canals Casals:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Juan Alberto Romero Baena:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation. **Alessandro Valls Pau:** Software. **Lluís Trilla:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

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Appendix A. BMS framework specification

The following view presents an overall picture of all features a BMS system shall cover, independently of the architecture followed.

Fig. A.10. Feature classification within BMS software.

Appendix B. Relative criteria matrix of each scenario

The tables below present the specific qualitative values assigned to weight each criterion in each scenario according to Saaty's scale [47] (see Tables B.11–B.14).

Table B.11

Scenario 1 - Relative criteria matrix.

A/B	Memory	Accuracy	Time	Observability	Controllability
Memory	1	5	3	7	2
Accuracy	0.2	1	0.33	5	0.33
Time	0.33	3	1	5	0.33
Observability	0.14	0.2	0.2	1	0.14
Controllability	0.5	3	3	7	1

Table B.12

Scenario 2 - Relative criteria matrix.

A/B	Memory	Accuracy	Time	Observability	Controllability
Memory	1	3	0.5	7	7
Accuracy	0.33	1	0.2	5	5
Time	2	5	1	7	7
Observability	0.14	0.2	0.14	1	1
Controllability	0.14	0.2	0.14	1	1

Table B.13

Scenario 3 - Relative criteria matrix.

A/B	Memory	Accuracy	Time	Observability	Controllability
Memory	1	0.5	2	1	7
Accuracy	2	1	2	2	7
Time	0.5	0.5	1	0.5	5
Observability	1	0.5	2	1	5
Controllability	0.14	0.14	0.2	0.2	1

Table B.14

Scenario 4 - Relative criteria matrix.

A/B	Memory	Accuracy	Time	Observability	Controllability
Memory	1	0.5	0.5	2	0.5
Accuracy	2	1	0.5	2	0.5
Time	2	2	1	2	0.5
Observability	0.5	0.5	0.5	1	0.5
Controllability	2	2	2	2	1

Appendix C. AHP results

This appendix section includes all the results for AHP implementation.

Table C.15
Criteria weights for each scenario.

Criteria	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4
Memory	41.78%	30.28%	23.50%	14.33%
Accuracy	10.43%	15.51%	35.85%	18.67%
Time	16.71%	45.10%	14.84%	24.22%
Observability	4.08%	4.56%	21.90%	10.78%
Controllability	27.00%	4.56%	3.90%	32.00%

Table C.16
Raw comparison of AHP alternative priority vectors for all the assessed criteria: Accuracy, Memory, Execution time, Observability, and Controllability.

	Accuracy	Memory	Execution time	Observability	Controllability
TPA	0.03193	0.26601	0.26954	0.03715	0.15041
Pade2	0.06792	0.26601	0.17639	0.03730	0.04826
Pade3	0.15756	0.07616	0.06549	0.15035	0.10554
Pade4	0.30201	0.02482	0.02261	0.39243	0.14848
HK2	0.04046	0.26601	0.31761	0.03713	0.11679
HK3	0.11953	0.07616	0.11325	0.13310	0.20329
HK4	0.28058	0.02482	0.03511	0.21254	0.22723

Appendix D. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matcom.2026.02.015>.

Data availability

Data and codes derived from the present article are available upon request. To request the data, contact the corresponding author of the article.

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